

Kinetics of Hydrolysis of Methyl Hydroxy and Methyl Methoxy Benzoates using Aquo-organic Solvents

BEENA RAWAT and H. S. RAMA*

Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, M. S. University of Baroda, Baroda-390 002

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Substituents on the substrate and the presence of water miscible cosolvents in the reaction medium play an important role in the redox as well as hydrolysis kinetics¹. Parker² predicted on the basis of solvation phenomenon that the rate of ester hydrolysis increased by dipolar aprotic solvent like DMSO. Bender and Thomas³ carried out the study on a number of substituted benzoates. We report in this communication the results of hydrolysis kinetics of some substituted (methyl, *o*-hydroxy, *o*-*m*- and *p*-methoxy) benzoates in aqueous solutions containing water miscible cosolvent (*N,N'*-dimethylformamide, dioxane or ethan α l).

Results and Discussion

Solvent effect : From Table 1 it is observed that the rate constant of alkaline hydrolysis of methyl substituted benzoates decreases with increasing percentage of cosolvent. Although the dielectric constant of dioxane is much less than that of DMF, the rate constants of hydrolysis in aqueous dioxane was found to be much higher than that in aqueous DMF. These results indicate that there are two effects of cosolvents, namely ion-solvent and solvent-solvent interactions. Both the effects are imperative. One may enhance and other may hinder the progress of the reaction, and ultimately the rate constant depends on the magnitude of the two effects. It is possible that the rate of reaction changes as a result of the change in solvation of either reactant or transition state.

Substitution effect : The rate of alkaline hydrolysis depends on the ability of OH⁻ ion to attack carbonyl group. In case of *o*-hydroxy-ester there is intramolecular hydrogen bonding due to the presence of OH group in the close proximity of COOCH₃ group in the molecule, whereas such intramolecular hydrogen bonding is not possible in *o*-methoxy ester and hence, the attack of OH⁻ ion

on C=O becomes easier in case of methyl *o*-methoxybenzoate and this explains the two- to four-fold increase of rate constants (Table 1).

Methoxy group is having a negative inductive effect which falls off with distance as we go from *o* → *m* → *p* but there will be an electron-donating mesomeric effect when methoxy is in *ortho* or *para* position, whereas, *meta* position is not affected. This can be explained in terms of resonance structure. When methoxy-esters are in *ortho* or *para* position, there is resonance interaction of groups which is not possible in transition state (Chart 1).

Chart 1

Thus the stability of ester relative to its transition state is increased. When two groups are in *meta* position with respect to each other, such resonance interactions are not possible. Thus one can expect electron density on the carbonyl carbon in *meta* position to be less and hence, the attack of OH⁻ is more feasible than that when methoxy is in *ortho* or *para* position and, therefore, a higher rate of hydrolysis for methyl in *m*-methoxybenzoate.

The hydrolysis of methyl *p*-hydroxybenzoate monitored by spectral method shows that it is very slow⁴. However, methyl *p*-methoxybenzoate shows a very high rate constant. The possible reason of this difference in the behaviour of these two esters could be attributed to the difference in the resonance structure (Chart 2). The resonance structure is stable, hence it could be possible that this structure prevents the hydrolysis of ester.

TABLE 1—RATE CONSTANTS ($k, \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$) OF METHYL SALICYLATE AND METHYL *o*-, *m*- and *p*-METHOXYBENZOATES
 Alkali = 0.01 mol dm^{-3}

	Dioxane			Ethanol			DMF		
	10	30	50	10	30	50	10	30	50
Temp. = 30°									
Methyl salicylate	4.80	3.75	3.30	4.50	3.09	1.26	—	—	—
Methyl <i>o</i> -methoxybenzoate	20.80	12.30	9.50	20.99	14.70	7.78	—	—	—
Methyl <i>m</i> -methoxybenzoate	25.60	20.30	7.59	20.00	16.60	5.70	14.80	11.00	7.65
Methyl <i>p</i> -methoxybenzoate	14.45	9.58	5.50	—	—	3.70	6.90	5.00	2.66
Temp. = 35°									
Methyl salicylate	17.60	9.10	8.90	6.60	4.90	2.20	—	—	—
Methyl <i>o</i> -methoxybenzoate	29.50	25.30	17.00	30.20	23.30	16.60	—	—	—
Methyl <i>m</i> -methoxybenzoate	46.30	25.60	12.71	45.00	21.60	11.10	20.30	15.20	10.01
Methyl <i>p</i> -methoxybenzoate	22.80	12.00	9.28	—	—	6.70	17.50	16.50	12.50

Effect of temperature : The value of ΔG^\ddagger was found to increase, though slightly, with the increase in cosolvent content, showing desolvation of transition state.

Experimental

To obtain methyl *p*-hydroxybenzoate, known amount of *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid was treated with dry methanol and concentrated H_2SO_4 . The product was crystallised from aqueous alcohol.

Methyl *o*-methoxy-, *m*-methoxy- and *p*-methoxybenzoates were prepared from *o*-hydroxy-, *m*-hydroxy- and *p*-hydroxybenzoic acids respectively. The hydroxy-acid was first converted to methoxy acid and then converted to the ester by using dry methanol. Methyl *o*-methoxy- and *m*-methoxybenzoate were purified by distillation and methyl *p*-methoxybenzoate obtained in solid form was crystallised. The purity of the liquid and solid products was checked by b.p. and m.p. respectively.

All the other reagents were purified by literature method.

Chart 2

For kinetic study the reaction mixture consisted of alkali and calculated amount of ester in presence of a cosolvent. The progress of the reaction was monitored by withdrawing aliquots at regular

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interval of 5 min and running into excess of 0.01*N* HCl and back-titrating with standard dilute NaOH to phenolphthalein end-point. The experiment was carried out at 30 and 35°.

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